

ThinkPhoton !

Are you ready to discover the power of light ?

1. Among all Nobel prizes awarded since 2000 how many have paid tribute to a breakthrough related to photonics ?

- 1
- 4
- 11

Answer : 11^[1]

Explanation : The UN declared the year 2015 "The Year of Light", arguing that "the 21st century will depend as much on photonics as the 20th century depended on electronics^[2]"

2. Who said : " the point of the [invisibility] cloak was a grand challenge to tell the world that if we can do that, we can do anything " ?

- Harry Potter, wizard
- John Pendry, physicist
- George Lucas, movie director

Answer : John Pendry, physicist^[3]

Explanation : The device depicted in the lower right corner has a peculiar structure that allows it to guide light around the hidden object. This could be useful to improve military stealth.

3. Can you guess the price of a foldscope -an origami-based microscope with a small glass marble as a lens and able to magnify up to 2000 times-?

Answer : 1 euro

1. http://www.osa.org/en-us/about_osa/osa_nobel_laureates/

2. <http://www.light2015.org/Home/WhyLightMatters.html>

3. [http://www.independent.co.uk/news/science/sir-john-pendry-pioneer-of-the-](http://www.independent.co.uk/news/science/sir-john-pendry-pioneer-of-the-invisibility-cloak-wins-top-institute-of-physics-honour-8681272.html)

[invisibility-cloak-wins-top-institute-of-physics-honour-8681272.html](http://www.independent.co.uk/news/science/sir-john-pendry-pioneer-of-the-invisibility-cloak-wins-top-institute-of-physics-honour-8681272.html)

Explanation : Thanks to its low price, less than a euro, this microscope could improve tuberculosis and malaria screenings incredibly in developing countries, or serve as an educational tool for schoolchildren⁴.

4. This year, what type of technology will bring the light-equivalent of an average lightbulb to a million slum inhabitants living without electricity?
- A dynamo that supplies a lightbulb
 - A battery charged up by lightnings
 - A bottle filled with water, screwed through the ceiling

Answer : A bottle filled with water, screwed through the ceiling⁵

Explanation : Water refracts sunlight, thus concentrating it towards the inside of the room. An upgraded version, including a small solar panel and an LED can be used as a night light.

5. What is the component displayed on the lower right picture?

- An artificial retina
- A memory chip
- The smallest LED ever made

Answer : An artificial retina

4. <http://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0098781>
5. <http://literoflight.org/about-us/>

Explanation : Patients who received this retina and were initially blind can now locate doors and windows in a room, crosswalks and have the ability to read words when written with big letters⁶.

6. The SPHERE European scientific instrument, aimed at discovering exoplanets, has such a high resolution that it could perceive :

- a candle located in Milano from Paris
- a two-euro coin located 2 kilometers away
- an ant located 5 meters away

Answer : a candle located in Milano from Paris⁷

Explanation : Adaptive optics, a technology at the very heart of SPHERE, has initially been designed for astronomy with extraordinary success. Today it is also used for medical imaging or eye surgery.

7. What is the common point between a CD and a soap bubble ?

- The PC “ Spongebob bubble bustin’ ” game
- Their colors are due to the same phenomenon
- Both are round

Answer : Their colors are due to the same phenomenon

Explanation : A soap bubble, a CD or some types of butterfly wings have specific microstructures that make us see different colors depending on the observation angle : this is called iridescence⁸

8. What percentage of customers, with a 10% margin, would consider lighting as the first criterion when choosing a restaurant ?

6. <http://www.inserm.fr/thematiques/neurosciences-sciences-cognitives-neurologie-psychiatrie/dossiers-d-information/retine-artificielle>

7. <http://www.onera.fr/fr/actualites/premiere-lumiere-sphere-saxo>

8. [http://www.futura-sciences.com/magazines/nature/infos/dico/d/zoologie-iridescence-](http://www.futura-sciences.com/magazines/nature/infos/dico/d/zoologie-iridescence-10240/)

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Answer : 71%^[9]

Explanation : Lighting is an innovative sector. LED, which represented only 8% of the global lighting market in 2011, will count for 75% of a 100-billion-dollar-industry as soon as in 2020^[10]

9. By measuring the travelling time of a laser pulse, astronomers are able to determine the Earth-Moon distance. How precise is this measurement ?
- 4 millimeters
 - 17 kilometers
 - 2030 kilometers

Answer : 4 millimeters

Explanation : We know the Earth-Moon distance better than our own height ! This incredible measurement is possible thanks to the reflectors installed by American astronauts in the 1970's.^[11]

10. What can't infrared light help us do ?
- Reveal the underlying layers and sketches of paintings
 - Make night vision devices
 - Remotely brush your teeth

Answer : Remotely brush your teeth

Explanation : Infrared radiations have many applications. Did you know that a technology called "infrared reflectography" revealed three sketches on the back of Da Vinci's "*Saint Anne*"^[12]?

9. <http://www.lumiere2015.fr/vie-quotidienne/>

10. <http://www.lefigaro.fr/mon-figaro/2012/12/23/10001-20121223ARTFIG00029-1-essor-des-led-bouscule-les-acteurs-de-l-eclairage.php>

11. <http://culturesciencesphysique.ens-lyon.fr/ressource/laser-distance-terre-lune.xml>

12. http://next.liberation.fr/culture/2008/12/18/vinci-cote-pile_297079

